

Genetic analysis of the wheat yellow rust pathogen *Puccinia striiformis* f. sp. *tritici* in Bhutan reveals high levels of diversity

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***Puccinia striiformis* f. sp. *tritici* (*Pst*), the causal agent of wheat yellow rust, is a significant threat to wheat cultivation worldwide. Located in the Himalya region where *Pst* is known to undergo sexual reproduction, Bhutan has long been suspected as a hotspot for *Pst* diversity. In this study, we set out to conduct a preliminary assessment of the genetic diversity of *Pst* in the region using the Mobile And Real-time PLant disEase (MARPLE) diagnostics genotyping platform. A total of twenty-two *Pst* samples from five distinct regions in Bhutan were analysed. Phylogenetic analysis supported a high level of genetic diversity among *Pst* samples, which clustered into at least four distinct genetic lineages. All four genetic lineages were present in just 6 samples from a single, high elevation location in Gasa district. This initial analysis indicates that enhanced surveillance effects are needed to comprehensively define the *Pst* population in the region, where these highly diverse *Pst* strains could be acting to seed epidemics in Bhutan, neighbouring countries and beyond.**

Introduction

Wheat is one of the most cultivated cereal crops in Bhutan, following rice and maize in terms of production volume and agricultural importance. It is grown on farmlands particularly at higher altitudes, given its resilience to cool temperatures, moderate water requirements, and short growing seasons. However, over the past three decades the area used for wheat cultivation has faced a significant decline, from 13,000 hectares (ha) in 1997 to 843 ha sown and 746 ha harvested in 2024 (1). This decline is attributed to several interlinked factors, including the introduction of high-

yielding rice varieties, which have diverted farmers away from wheat cultivation. The socio-economic landscape of the country has also played a major role in this decline, with many farmers opting for more lucrative crops to circumvent mechanisation challenges, labour shortages and waning returns from farming (2). Climatic change, especially erratic rainfall patterns and fluctuating temperatures, along with the rise of biotic stressors and limited access to high-yielding and disease-resistant wheat varieties, are increasingly undermining cultivation.

Among the various biotic constraints on wheat production, one of the greatest threats is from the yellow rust pathogen *Puccinia striiformis* f. sp. *tritici* (*Pst*). In Bhutan's cooler wheat-growing regions *Pst* is a pervasive threat, resulting in consistent yield losses over the past three decades (3). In addition, *Pst* has a heteroecious lifecycle where it reproduces asexually on wheat and sexually on *Berberis* spp., with the latter leading to emergence of abundant novel pathogen genotypes (4). It is well recognized that sexual reproduction for *Pst* is seemingly currently restricted globally to the Himalaya region, that includes Bhutan (5). To date sexual reproduction of *Pst* in natural conditions has only been conclusively confirmed in China (6), but signals of high genetic diversity have been found in Pakistan, Nepal and Bhutan (7). Bhutan is also recognized as a global hotspot for *Berberis* diversity, with these plants being exceptionally abundant (8). Thus, posing a significant risk to escalating *Pst* diversity in the country. However, to date no mechanisms have existed within Bhutan to evaluate the genetic diversity of *Pst*, which is crucial for effective disease management and guiding breeding strategies. To address this gap, in 2025 the Mobile And Real-time PLant disEase (MARPLE) diagnostics system was introduced into Bhutan (9,10). This system uses a simple gene sequencing approach to facilitate near real-time, strain-level diagnostics of *Pst* and is highly suitable for implementation in resource-poor regions. Using this newly introduced system, we conducted a preliminary assessment of the current genetic diversity of the *Pst* population in Bhutan confirming high levels of *Pst* diversity across the region.

Materials and methods

Wheat leaf samples with symptoms typical of *Pst* infection were collected and processed following the MARPLE diagnostics pipeline as described previously (9,10). In brief, infected leaf samples were disrupted in lysis buffer (200 μ L; 10 mM Tris-HCl, 1 mM EDTA, 0.1% (w/v) SDS). Following centrifugation, the supernatant (150 μ L) was mixed with SeraSil-Mag™ 400 magnetic

beads (30 µL; Cytiva, Washington, USA) and binding buffer PB (360 µL; Qiagen, Manchester, UK), before incubating (5 min; room temperature) and allowing the DNA to bind to the beads. After a pellet was formed, the supernatant was removed, and the beads washed twice with ethanol (500 µL; 80%). DNA was recovered by adding elution buffer EB (50 µL; Qiagen, Manchester, UK), before incubating (5 min.; room temperature) and collecting the supernatant. PCR amplification was performed using the AmpliTaq Gold™ 360 Master Mix (Applied Biosystems, Massachusetts, USA) and the four MARPLE *Pst* primer pools (11). PCR products were cleaned using the same magnetic bead protocol as above. Resulting amplicons were pooled for each sample, libraries prepared and sequenced on the MinION Mk1B device using the SQK-PBK114.24 library preparation kit and Flow Cells FLO-MIN114 R10.4.1 (Oxford Nanopore Technologies, Oxford, UK). The resulting basecalled reads were used to perform bioinformatics analysis using the MARPLE diagnostics workflow (12).

Results

Twenty-two *Pst*-infected wheat leaf samples were collected from five regions across Bhutan. This included three samples taken from durum wheat (*Triticum turgidum* subsp. *durum*, cultivar Shakti) and nineteen samples taken from local bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) varieties (Fig. 1a). All samples were processed using the MARPLE diagnostics pipeline, where the sequence of 384 highly polymorphic genes was derived using nanopore sequencing (9,10). Samples with >40% amplification of these polymorphic genes are included in the final analysis. The success in amplification for the 22 field-collected *Pst* samples shown here, ranged between 40.3-84.2 % (Fig. 1b).

Fig. 1. Successful implementation of the MARPLE diagnostics workflow, allowed targeted sequencing of polymorphic genes in *Pst*. (a) Leaf sample infected with yellow rust (*Puccinia striiformis* f. sp. *tritici*, *Pst*) and leaf rust (*Puccinia triticina*, *Pt*), from a locally cultivated wheat crop. (b) MultiQC report from the MARPLE diagnostics workflow, showing on average high success rate in the targeted sequencing of the highly polymorphic *Pst* genes, used to genotype field samples.

Phylogenetic analysis was conducted within the MARPLE diagnostics pipeline to examine the clustering of the Bhutanese samples with 46 *Pst* samples that act as representatives of 13 major *Pst* race groups (9). This analysis indicated that the Bhutanese *Pst* samples were distributed across four main *Pst* clades that were largely distinct from the *Pst* representatives. The largest clade included 8 *Pst* samples that were from 4 of the 5 regions sampled. Two clades contained 6 samples each: (i) one clade containing 2 *Pst* samples from Bumthang, 1 sample from Gasa (3775 m), one from an unspecified location and 2 from Thimphu, and (ii) another clade containing 2 samples from Bumthang in the central region of Bhutan, 2 from the Haa valleys and one from Paro both in the west, with the closest relatives to this clade the two samples from the Gasa region. Finally, one single *Pst* sample grouped alone and was collected in the Gasa region. It was notable that 6 samples collected from a very limited geographic area (<3km²) in Gasa included all 4 distinct *Pst* clades, indicating very high genetic diversity at this location.

Fig. 2. Analysis of *Pst*-infected field samples from Bhutan reveal a wide genetic diversity of the pathogen across the country. The MARPLE diagnostics pipeline was used to classify *Pst*-infected samples in Bhutan in one of 13 genetic groups, using a set of 384 highly polymorphic *Pst* genes. The phylogeny was constructed using an approximate maximum-likelihood model. The elevation of the locations where the samples were collected are given next to the district symbol in meters above sea level.

Conclusion

Wheat cultivation in Bhutan is under constant threat by biotic stressors, such as yellow rust. Here, we deployed our MARPLE diagnostics method and conducted a preliminary assessment of *Pst* diversity in Bhutan. This analysis uncovered high levels of genetic diversity within the *Pst* population across the country and identified a single high elevation location (Gasa) with very high *Pst* genetic diversity. Results highlight the need for more comprehensive surveillance and detailed genetic analysis to characterise the full diversity of *Pst* isolates present in Bhutan. This new knowledge can then help guide future disease management decisions to better protect Bhutan, neighbouring countries and beyond from yellow rust outbreaks that could be seeded by *Pst* isolates originating in Bhutan.

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